

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PHONETIC AND GRAPHIC ASPECTS OF REALIA-WORDS

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Abstract

During intercultural communication, translators often encounter words and phrases with certain cultural suggestions and references called realia-words.

This article explores the significance of the phonetic and graphic aspects of realia-words in the process of translation and cultural message transmission. By examining elements such as sounds, accent, intonation, punctuation marks, capitalization, and diacritics, we delve into how they contribute to the creation of coherent and authentic texts that are in harmony with cultural specificities. Correct utilization of these aspects not only aids in avoiding confusion and pronunciation errors but also ensures the preservation of authenticity and clarity in the conveyed message. Attention to the phonetic and graphic aspects of realia-words is essential in achieving accurate communication and conveying cultural values effectively. Through an in-depth analysis, this article emphasizes the role of these linguistic elements in fostering precise cultural transmission and facilitating a deeper understanding of diverse cultural experiences.

This topic was chosen due to the fact that it is an important aspect of the language and has a theoretical and practical importance, being an object of study for many translators, linguists and specialists in the field.

Keywords: phonetic aspects, graphic aspects, realia-words, translation, cultural transmission, cultural specificities.

Introduction

Realia-words are linguistic units used by both writers and translators of literary texts. In the process of translation, it is necessary to take into account the linguistic peculiarities of realia-words in terms of structure, phonetic and graphic aspects, grammatical form, meaning, etc., in order to create a coherent and homogeneous text. The focus of this paper lies in the thorough examination of the phonetic and graphic aspects, with particular emphasis on examples derived from the Romanian text *Amintiri din copilărie* (I. Creangă) [2]. However, it is important to note that we have also included pertinent examples extracted from English texts such as *Bridget Jones's Diary* (H. Fielding) [6], and *Memoirs of a Geisha* (A. Golden) [7].

The text *Amintiri din copilărie* abounds in realia-words, which refer to specific aspects of Romanian culture. These lexemes are rooted in traditions, customs, landscapes, characters, and events that are specific to Romania and reflect a distinct cultural reality. Through these words, the author manages to create an authentic atmosphere and convey to the readers the emotions, experiences, and cultural peculiarities of his time. These realia-words contribute to the creation of a strong cultural identity and the preservation of Romanian traditions and values in literature. They have a powerful emotional impact and evoke a sense of belonging to Romanian culture and history.

The text *Bridget Jones's Diary* is filled with realia-words that refer to various cultures, such as British, American, French, Italian, Portuguese, German, and others. These lexemes reflect specific aspects of each mentioned culture and add a rich and diverse cultural dimension to the story of the main character. The use

of realia-words provides the readers with an opportunity to familiarize themselves with phrases, terms, customs, and traditions specific to each culture mentioned in the text. These lexemes contribute to the authenticity and truthfulness of the narrative, adding a sense of realism and connecting the readers with various cultural aspects and experiences unique to each country. This cultural diversity represented through realia-words from different languages and cultures helps create a multicultural and multiethnic framework.

The text *Memoirs of a Geisha* is a literary work rich in realia-words that refer to Japanese culture. These realia-words contribute to creating an authentic atmosphere and conveying specific cultural details of Japan. These realia-words not only describe objects, practices, and institutions specific to Japanese culture but also bring to the forefront essential aspects of Japanese life and mentality. They help build the atmosphere and cultural context in which the characters' story unfolds and provide readers with an opportunity to familiarize themselves with Japanese traditions and values. The use of realia-words contributes to the authenticity and realism of the text, offering readers a deep cultural and linguistic experience. These words serve to transport readers to Japan, helping them understand and feel the emotions and experiences of the characters more deeply.

The phonetic and graphic aspects of realia-words that we are going to analyze are: sound, accent, intonation, punctuation marks, capitalization, and diacritics.

The sound

Sounds themselves do not have a semantic content, but they allow us to distinguish between lexemes that have different semantic content. For example, the combination of sounds [cot] constitutes a lexical unit

that has a specific meaning (an old unit of measurement [5]). If we change the first sound, we obtain new lexemes with different semantic content: [lot], [pot], [vot], [tot], [iot], [got], [fot], [șot].

The sound, analyzed from a functional perspective, is called a phoneme. Phonemes help not only in identifying different lexemes but also in distinguishing between forms of the same lexeme: *cuptor – cuptorul – cuptoare – cuptoarele – cuptorului – cuptoarelor; răzeș – răzeșul – răzeși – răzeșii – răzeșului – răzeșilor*.

Typically, each letter in the Romanian language represents a single sound (i.e., a phoneme). However, there are exceptions:

- a letter can produce different sounds;
- a sound can be expressed by two or three letters;
- a sound can be expressed by a combination of letters;

1. The letter *a* produces different sounds in realia-words borrowed from other languages: [æ] barrister, [a:] Mark, [er] Mavis.

2. The letters *i* and *y* represent the same sound [i] in realia-words of different origins: *mir, baci, cărpaci, loby, Mary, Darcy*.

3. The letters *c* and *g* represent the consonants [c] and [g] (*corhană, catihis, căruță, Cotârgaș, crășmă, cojocar, cotruță, covată, glas*), but also the affricates [č] and [ğ] when they precede the letters *e* and *i* (*ceaslov, concina, ceață, Ciubuc, Cărăgița, cimpoi*).

4. The letter *h* in some realia-words does not represent any sound but indicates the palatalization of the letters *g* and *c*: *Ghindăoanii, Ghica-vodă, Gheorghe, chiolhănos, Chiriac, Costache, chiraleisa*.

The accent

The accent of a lexeme involves the phonetic means of emphasizing a syllable in a word or phrase, such as the intensity of voice, rising tone, or length of pronunciation. Such a syllable serves as a focal point around which the sound entity forming the lexeme is “organized”. The accent helps distinguish words that have the same sounds [1, p. 7]. In the Romanian language, the accent can fall on different syllables. For example, the polysemous lexemes: a) *pára* - b) *pará* have the following meanings [5]:

- 1. flame, 2. fruit of the pear tree, 3. denomination given to objects, technical parts, etc., in the shape of a pear.
- 1. a small Turkish silver coin that circulated in the Romanian countries in the 18th-19th centuries, 2. money, 3. to evade an opponent's attack by means of a counterattack in a duel, fencing, etc. The realia-word has the meaning b1.

Accent can play a significant role in determining the meaning of a word in some languages, such as Romanian. Therefore, marking the accent of realia-words can ensure that the intended meaning is preserved in the target language. It also provides clarity and accuracy as it can help disambiguate words that may be spelled the same but have different meanings.

Realia-words are often used to provide context and specificity to a sentence or phrase, indicating the cultural background of the speaker or writer. Accents can be an essential part of a word in a culture, and the absence of accent marking can lead to confusion or misunderstanding.

When a translator introduces a new realia-word into the text, unfamiliar to the reader, the translator should, at least when using this word for the first time in the text, mark the vowel on which the stress falls. Otherwise, there are situations where the mispronunciation of the foreign word remains in the recipient's memory forever. Accent marking is important in translation, especially when dealing with related languages, because in the mind of an ordinary recipient, the lexical proximity of units implies phonetic proximity as well. Thus, the word is not pronounced according to the rules of the source language but according to those of the target language, and naturally, the stress may not fall on the correct syllable. Once distorted realia-words enter mass media texts, they are widely distributed and become fixed in the target language to such an extent that correcting the pronunciation is usually impossible.

Intonation

Intonation constitutes a combination of phonetic features (rhythm, melody, tempo, intensity, timbre) that help express expressive and emotional nuances, as well as syntactic values and categories. Through intonation, we distinguish different types of utterances that have the same composition [1, p. 7]. For example: 1. *A venit Vodă.*; 2. *A venit Vodă?*; 3. *A venit Vodă!* In the first sentence, we state a fact, in the second, we request information, and in the third, we express an emotional state.

Logical or syntactic stress (sentence stress) is a phonetic feature that helps distinguish between utterances that have identical lexical and structural composition. For example: 1. *Vodă are să treacă pe acolo.* 2. *Vodă are să treacă pe acolo.*

As we can observe from the examples above, stress is studied by phonetics, but it represents an element that helps differentiate words, pertaining to lexicon and morphology. Intonation and logical stress, as elements that aid in expressing the values of utterances, refer to syntax.

Punctuation marks

We have identified the following punctuation marks: the hyphen, the apostrophe, and the period.

The hyphen is used to connect two or more words that are pronounced together. Functioning as such, it serves the following purposes graphically:

- the disappearance or elision of one of the two vowels: *Nic-a lui Costache, Nic-a Petricăi, Nic-a lui Ștefan a Petrei, Nic-a lui Constantin a Cosmei*;
- the dropping of the enclitic article *-l*: *Podu-Leloaiiei, vâru-meu Ion Mogorogea*;
- the combination of a noun and a pronominal adjective: *soră-ta Ioana, vâru-meu Ion Mogorogea*;
- the writing of compound realia-words: *Valea-Seacă, Târgul-Frumos, Miezul-Păresii, pierde-vară*.

The apostrophe serves the following graphical purposes:

- the absence of the initial digits in the notation of a year: '82 *Pauillac*;

- the possessive relationship in English (genitive case): *Nigel Coles' wife*, *Audrey*, *Reader's Digest*.

The period, as a punctuation mark, is used in abbreviations: *I.* (=Ion) *Creangă*, *B.* (=Bridget) *Jones*. Abbreviations containing word fragments are written without a period: *British Telecom* (=Telecommunications), as well as common abbreviations: *BBC1* (=British Broadcasting Corporation's television channel 1), *M&S* (=Marks & Spencer), *st* (=stone), *lb* (=pound), *oz* (=ounce).

Capitalization

Capitalization varies from language to language. However, we can say that it conveys additional information compared to lowercase writing. Regarding realia-words, we have identified the following uses:

1. marking the beginning of a sentence: *Simon is coming round.*, *Crăsmărița, cum ne-a văzut, pe loc ne-a sărit înainte și ne-a dus deoparte, într-o odaie mare, cu obloane la ferești și podiță pe jos, unde eram numai înde noi și crăsmărița, când poftea, ca la casa ei.*, *Catihetul, care făcea ziua noapte și noaptea zi, jucând stos, rar venea pe la școală.*;

2. abbreviations: *BBC1* (=British Broadcasting Corporation), *M1* (=motorway), *M6*, *RSC* (=Royal Shakespeare Company);

3. graphic distinction between proper nouns and common nouns (*Boboteaza*, *Vinerea Seacă*, *Cosmo*, *Bruce Springsteen*, *Jamie*):

- personal names (first names, surnames), nicknames: *Alecu Baloș*, *Ciubuc Clopotarul*, *Irinuca*, *Zaharia Simionescu*, *Ion Torcălău*;

- simple geographical names: *Iași*, *Bistrița*, *Moldova*, *Baia*, *Siret*, *Gion*, *Kyoto*, *Japan*, *Shirakawa*, *Seoul*;

- simple names of holidays: *Moși*, *Paști*, *Crăciun*;

- compound geographical names (excluding auxiliary words): *Munții Neamțului*, *Dealul Omului*, *Podul de la Timișești*;

- compound geographical names, in which the generic term together with the constituent elements are conceived as a single unit: *Pârăul Cârjei*, *Valea-Seacă*, *Târgul-Frumos*, *Kamo River*, *Osaka Bay*, *Inland Sea*, *Shijo Avenue* (if the generic term is not an organic part of the geographic name, in this case, it is written with a lowercase initial letter: *satul Bălțatești*, *satul Topolița*, *mahalaua Pometea*, *ulița Buciumenii*, *podul Cărăgiței*);

- compound names of state, political, national or international organizations, institutions, and enterprises: *Japan Coastal Seafood Company*;

- compound names of holidays: *Sâmbăta lui Lazăr*, *Duminica Mare*, *Sfântul Dumitru*, *Sânt Ilie*.

Examples of realia-words written with lowercase initial letters are:

1. names of mythical beings used as common nouns: *strigoi*, *balaur*, *zmeu*;

2. names of objects or units of measurement: *catrință*, *desagă*, *opincă*, *ițari*, *ocă*, *dimerlie*, *cot*;

3. names of individuals based on their place of residence: *mocan*, *humuleștean*, *plăieș*, *polon*, *neamț*;

4. names of state, religious, military, and political functions: *mitropolit*, *popă*, *vornic*, *vătăman*, *mazil*.

Diacritical Marks

A diacritical mark is a graphic sign placed above or below a letter to indicate a specific pronunciation or to distinguish between the meanings of two words. The Romanian language uses five diacritical marks: ă, â, î, ș, ț. These diacritical marks have specific appearances and names: breve (Ă, ă), circumflex (Â â, Î î), and undercomma (Ș ș, Ț ț) [8].

The word “diacritic” derives from the Greek word “diakritikos”, which means “separate” or “able to distinguish”, and is based on the prefix “dia-” meaning “through” and the verb “krinein”, meaning “to separate” [9].

In the Romanian language, incorrect writing without diacritical marks can lead to non-existent words, and some of them can be misinterpreted. This also applies to translations from Romanian into English. For example:

Source Text	Target Text
<i>Corăbiasca</i> [2, p. 209]	<i>the Corabiasca</i> [3]
	<i>the corăbieasca</i> [4,p. 85]
<i>Țiitura</i> [2, p. 209]	<i>the Tiitura</i> [3]
<i>moș Vasile Țandură</i>	<i>old Vasile Tandură</i> [3],
[2, p. 170]	[4, p. 276]
<i>Mihai scripcarul din Humulești</i> [2, p. 230]	<i>Mihai, the Humulești fiddler</i> [4, p. 116]

N. Grigorie-Lăcrița states that individuals who write without diacritics demonstrate a lack of respect towards their audience. The correct use of diacritics represents an “indicator of the level of culture and professionalism” [8]. The proper use of diacritical marks in a translation can help not only in avoiding confusion and incorrect pronunciation but also in preserving the original cultural context of the text and making the translation appear more authentic.

Conclusion

The phonetic and graphic aspects of realia-words represent significant elements in the process of translation and cultural message transmission. Sounds, accent, intonation, punctuation marks, capitalization, and diacritics all contribute to the creation of a coherent, authentic, and culturally harmonious text. The correct utilization of these aspects not only helps avoid confusion and pronunciation errors but also preserves the authenticity and clarity of the conveyed message. Thus, attention to the phonetic and graphic aspects of realia-words is crucial in ensuring accurate communication and appropriate transmission of specific cultural values and traits.

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